

dedalus

Bringing **comfort** and **power**
connection for everyday living

Educational → Kit

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Foreword

Across Europe, households account for **about 26% of the EU's final energy consumption**¹, and the building sector as a whole is responsible for roughly **40% of total energy use and 36% of CO₂ emissions**. Most of this energy - nearly 80% in residential buildings (Fig. 1) - is used for heating and cooling, while electricity demand from appliances, lighting, and connected devices keeps rising.

This makes **buildings a crucial component of the European energy transition**. In the past, the balance between energy supply and demand was relatively simple: generation came from large fossil-fuel plants, and consumption followed predictable daily and seasonal patterns. Today, the increasing share of **renewable energy sources** - such as wind and solar - has made generation more variable and less controllable. As a result, system flexibility **has become a key requirement**.

FIG. 1

Final energy consumption in the residential sector by fuel in 2023

Source: EUROSTAT

One of the most promising strategies to provide flexibility is **Demand Response (DR)** - adapting electricity consumption to grid conditions, for instance, by reducing or shifting loads during peak hours or when renewable generation is low.

While industrial and commercial sectors have already embraced DR², the **residential sector remains largely untapped**. Homes possess significant flexibility potential, thanks to new technologies like smart thermostats, connected appliances, home batteries, and heat pumps. However, the challenge lies not only in technology but also in **human behaviour, comfort perception, and social acceptance**.

Against this backdrop, the **DEDALUS project**³ was set up to explore how Europe's residential sector can actively contribute to energy flexibility while preserving comfort, social inclusion, and affordability. By combining social sciences, digital technologies, and new business models, **DEDALUS transforms the concept of DR into a user-centred ecosystem - one that empowers residents, supports local communities, and strengthens the resilience of the energy system**.

This **educational kit** introduces students to the main concepts, technologies, and methodologies behind residential DR.

It provides:

- An overview of energy flexibility tools, comfort flexibility service, and district-level energy management system;
- Case studies from DEDALUS pilot sites;
- A summary of European research and innovation projects that laid the groundwork for DEDALUS, as presented in this Annex.

By studying the **DEDALUS approach**, students will gain a deeper understanding of both the **technical and human factors** driving Europe's evolving energy landscape - and the role they can play in shaping **smarter, more flexible, and more sustainable buildings**.

2

DEDALUS Approach

The **DEDALUS approach involves** a socially inclusive and multi-energy demand response ecosystem for residential buildings.

It integrates three complementary perspectives:

- **Social and behavioural**, studying how people engage with energy and how non-financial motivations - such as comfort and well-being - influence participation;
- **Technological**, combining artificial intelligence, the internet of things, blockchain, and digital twins to predict, manage, and optimise energy use;
- **Business-oriented**, developing models that make DR economically viable and scalable across Europe.

This holistic approach (Fig. 2) - spanning from user engagement and data governance to cross-commodity flexibility management - will foster inclusive, participatory DR ecosystems that benefit residents, energy stakeholders, and broader societal goals.

FIG. 2

An overview of the three DEDALUS layers and their expected impacts

Business level

15%

Increase in the energy-efficient of the pilot buildings, and cheaper energy bills for residents thanks to DR

15%

Cost reduction of the overall energy system

>25%

Reduction of demand response transaction costs after 5 years

Technological level

12

Smart residential asset types ready for demand response after 3 years

≥ 7

New aggregation models and data-driven services

≥ 2

Digital twins to facilitate consumer activation and market participation

Social level

45%

Increased share of energy consumption data by active consumers after 5 years

15-20%

Increased share of aggregated flexibility achieved by piloted assets

>18-20%

Carbon emission reduction in the areas of the 7 pilots

2.1 PILOT DEMONSTRATIONS

The DEDALUS pilot sites cover **seven diverse residential contexts across Europe**⁴ - from elderly cohousing and social housing complexes to university campuses and energy communities equipped with PV, batteries and EV charging. This geographical and socio-economic variety provides a robust testbed for assessing residential demand response under real operating conditions, different climatic zones, and heterogeneous digital infrastructures.

FIG. 3

Geographical distribution of the DEDALUS pilots and their deployed technologies

- 1 SPAIN** - District-level DR for increasing community-level self-consumption while providing flexibility to local DSO
- 2 IRELAND** - Integration of residential heating flexibility into broader energy system services, contributing to decarbonization goals and supporting grid stability
- 3 ITALY** - Trading off comfort with energy consumption in DR programs for elderly people living in serviced apartments
- 4 AUSTRIA** - Flexibility pre-aggregation for building-level energy community
- 5 DENMARK** - Energy efficiency and DR optimal interactions between district heating and electricity networks in social housing
- 6 ROMANIA** - Blockchain solutions for DR Management and flexibility aggregation
- 7 GREECE** - Multi-value DR for multi-segments of residential energy (electricity and gas) consumers

The pilots include front-runner demonstrators in Austria, Denmark, Greece, Italy, and Spain, complemented by replication pilots in Ireland and Romania. Together, they offer a comprehensive picture of how DEDALUS solutions can support households, building managers, energy communities, and local utilities in unlocking flexibility, improving comfort, and increasing the use of renewable energy at different scales.

3

Innovative Services for Residential Flexibility

Three innovative services are now available to enhance energy flexibility in residential buildings. **Each service represents a different but complementary layer of the DEDALUS ecosystem:**

- **ENERGY FLEXIBILITY TOOL:** designed to quantify and forecast the flexibility potential of residential and district-level energy systems.
- **COMFORT FLEXIBILITY SERVICE:** focused on maintaining occupants' comfort and well-being while participating in demand response events.
- **DISTRICT-LEVEL ENERGY MANAGEMENT SYSTEM:** enabling coordinated and optimized operation of shared assets within energy communities.

● ENERGY FLEXIBILITY TOOL

The **DEDALUS flexibility assessment tool (FLEXiT)** supports both aggregated (building-level) and disaggregated (device-level) flexibility analysis. At the aggregated level, the methodology uses historical electricity consumption and PV production to forecast energy profiles, derive baselines, and quantify flexibility via energy flexibility indicators (EFIs). At the device level, **non-intrusive load monitoring (NILM)** and advanced **ML** models are used to identify flexible vs. non-flexible loads and estimate their contribution to overall flexibility.

The core objective is to provide a **flexibility prediction model** that enhances DR performance and energy efficiency. **Long short-term memory (LSTM)** neural networks forecast next-day consumption and production, while EFIs, baseline, and min/max flexibility bands quantify the realistic range of adjustments. This methodology is implemented in FLEXiT, a tool that allows energy aggregators, building operators, and pilot users to upload data, configure models, and obtain actionable insights.

The main functionalities are:

1. ENERGY FORECASTING

LSTM models forecast consumption and PV production using pre-processed historical data with temporal features (month, hour, day-of-week). At the building level, forecasts cover up to 7 days ahead, at the device level, short-term disaggregated forecasts cover up to 3 hours ahead.

2. BASELINE AND FLEXIBILITY THRESHOLDS

For each target day, the tool computes hourly baselines and min/max flexibility levels from the previous 30 days of the same weekday, for both consumption and generation. These determine the flexibility band against which deviations are evaluated.

3. ENERGY FLEXIBILITY INDICATORS (EFIs)

EFIs express, in percentage terms, the potential hourly increase or decrease of consumption or generation relative to the baseline, for both consumers and prosumers. Additional EFIs are calculated over four time intervals (A-D) that combine high/low consumption and production conditions.

4. DEVICE-LEVEL DISAGGREGATION AND FLEXIBILITY

NILM techniques based on Denoising Autoencoder (DAE) and Cluster-Optimised DAE (C-DAE) models disaggregate total demand into appliance-level profiles (e.g. refrigerator, washing machine, dishwasher). Loads are classified as flexible or non-flexible, and device-level flexibility ratios are computed (share of flexible loads in total load, or load shifted to PV-rich periods for prosumers).

5. TIME-INTERVAL CATEGORISATION FOR DR

Forecasts are segmented into four time intervals (A-D) according to predicted high/low consumption and production. For each interval, aggregated EFIs are computed, supporting targeted DR strategies such as peak shaving, valley filling and shifting flexible loads to high-PV hours.

6. VISUALISATION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

A ReactJS-based dashboard provides historical analytics, forecast plots (baseline and flexibility bands), hourly EFIs, time-interval classifications and disaggregated flexibility curves. The tool generates concise suggestions (e.g. best hours to run flexible appliances) to support operational DR actions and planning.

FURTHER INSIGHTS INTO THE SERVICE

The flexibility assessment tool builds on a consolidated body of peer-reviewed research, covering aggregated flexibility forecasting, device-level NILM and platform-level operationalisation.

- **Aggregated building-level flexibility and EFIs are detailed in:**

1. (2024), “*Aggregated Flexibility Dynamic Forecasting of Residential Energy Prosumers for DR Programs*”, IEEE IISA.⁵
1. (2025), “*A data-driven framework for estimating residential energy flexibility for aggregated demand-side management*”, Sustainable Energy, Grids and Networks, 43.⁶

These works describe the end-to-end LSTM-based forecasting pipeline, baseline and min/max flexibility calculation, and EFI formulation, validated on a real Austrian prosumer building with PV, storage and EV charging.

- **Device-level NILM is presented in:** (2025), “Denoising Autoencoder for Appliance-Specific Energy Disaggregation in Residential Settings”, IEEE MetroLivEnv.⁷

This paper introduces the DAE and C-DAE architectures for appliance-level disaggregation, evaluates them against classical NILM baselines, and demonstrates significant improvements in Recall, F1 Score and RMSE on UKDALE, REDD and Greek pilot data.

- **Integrated software platform (FLEXiT) is presented in:** (2025), “*FLEXiT: A platform for estimating residential energy flexibility for aggregated & disaggregated demand-side management*”, SoftwareX, 32, 102433.⁸

FLEXiT provides the full-stack web platform that operationalises these methodologies, coupling LSTM-based 1–7 day aggregated forecasts, DAE-based appliance disaggregation, dynamic 30-day weekday baselines and EFIs within a modular, containerised environment.

● COMFORT FLEXIBILITY SERVICE

The **Comfort Flexibility Service (CFS)** provides a **comfort-based flexibility model** that ensures the health and well-being of residents during DR events. It integrates a variety of sensors and monitoring systems to measure indoor environmental quality - including thermal, acoustic, visual, and air parameters - together with local weather station data, all connected to a cloud-based platform.

By applying advanced learning techniques, the system incorporates user behaviour and preferences, captured through **Thermal Sensation Votes (TSV)**, to enable a personalised approach to comfort management. This data-driven method optimises the balance among:

- **User comfort**
- **Energy consumption**
- **Building performance**

As a result, the service generates comfort flexibility actions that can dynamically reshape building energy demand during DR events. It ensures a truly user-centric and adaptive Demand Response framework, improving both energy efficiency and occupant comfort in residential buildings.

SERVICE ARCHITECTURE

The **Comfort Flexibility Service** is structured around three main functional blocks:

1. BUILDING LEVEL

This phase covers **data acquisition through non-intrusive sensors installed in buildings or individual apartments**. The sensors continuously collect information about temperature, humidity, air quality, lighting, and noise levels.

2. COMFORT FLEXIBILITY MODEL

The collected data are processed to assess the building's operating conditions and evaluate possible comfort flexibility options. **The model computes optimal scenarios that balance energy efficiency and user comfort under varying environmental and occupancy conditions.**

3. DECISION PHASE

In this stage, the outcomes from the flexibility model are combined with real-time grid requests. Based on this integration, the system generates the optimal trade-off between comfort and energy efficiency for each specific situation.

MODEL OUTPUTS AND USER INTERACTION

The output of the comfort flexibility model consists of **recommendations defining the optimal indoor temperature (T_{in}) and relative humidity (RH) profiles for the following day**. These are presented hourly according to three operational targets:

1. **Optimal comfort** while minimising energy consumption;
2. **Acceptable comfort** with further reduction of energy consumption;
3. **Maximum energy savings** with limited regard for comfort preferences.

These recommendations are then provided to the end user - or to the building manager - who selects the option that best suits the residents' needs. If the grid operator requests a specific load reduction within a given time window, the system automatically applies the most suitable comfort profile proposed for that event. The building or apartment control system is then configured accordingly.

STAKEHOLDER BENEFITS

The service is designed to support both **residents** and **building managers**.

- **Residents can participate directly in flexibility programs** by signing agreements with grid operators and receiving **financial incentives** for adjusting their energy use during DR events.
- **Building or apartment managers can maintain a consistent level of comfort across all units without requiring residents to interact with the grid.** The process can be delegated to an **automated management system**, which optimises building performance and ensures occupant well-being at all times.

FURTHER INSIGHTS INTO THE SERVICE

The service is based on research presented in the paper “*Methodological Approach for Optimizing Demand Response in Building Energy Management through AI-Enhanced Comfort-Based Flexibility Models*”⁹ which introduces an innovative framework that integrates artificial intelligence to enhance demand response strategies in building energy management. By leveraging AI, the approach aims to balance energy efficiency with occupant comfort, ensuring that energy consumption is optimised without compromising the well-being of building occupants. This methodology is particularly relevant for smart building applications where adaptive and personalised energy management is crucial.

● DISTRICT-LEVEL ENERGY MANAGEMENT SYSTEM

The **District-level Energy Management system** (EMS) evolves from previous European initiatives and introduces multi-commodity optimisation and user-centric demand response capabilities. This enables aggregated control of flexible loads. This service introduces an **innovative district-level approach to DR**, engaging the entire energy value chain - from end users to local retailers and public administrations.

Unlike conventional DR initiatives, which typically focus on individual buildings, this system leverages **collective assets** such as shared **photovoltaic** (PV) systems and district-scale batteries. By enabling aggregated management of generation, storage, and flexible loads (e.g. heat pumps and electric vehicle

chargers), it enhances both grid stability and community participation. In a context of high market volatility and ongoing energy crises, this system not only facilitates active consumer participation in DR programs but also contributes to economic resilience for **small local retailers**. Through the integration of **time-of-use tariffs, collective self-consumption schemes, and dynamic storage management**, it demonstrates how community-scale DR can balance comfort, efficiency, and market participation — representing a significant step beyond current state-of-the-art residential DR practices.

SYSTEM OBJECTIVES AND METHODOLOGY

The district-level EMS is designed to optimise the operation of **residential energy communities**. It considers the operational characteristics and configurations of community assets, forecasts of renewable generation and demand, and the flexibility needs of end users (for example, charging cycles of electric vehicles).

By formulating and solving a **nonlinear optimisation problem** subject to the physical and operational constraints of the community, the system minimises overall energy costs while maintaining user comfort and supporting renewable integration.

The EMS can be integrated as a **district-level optimisation module** within the higher-level architecture of an energy community. It communicates seamlessly with other modules — for instance, a pre-aggregation framework for retrieving forecasts and publishing management commands — ensuring full interoperability and scalability.

FUNCTIONALITIES

The tool provides several key functionalities:

1. SHARED STORAGE MANAGEMENT

Determines the **optimal charging and discharging schedule for shared battery systems**, producing the corresponding power setpoints. Batteries are used to store surplus renewable energy or to purchase electricity during low-price periods, following the computed optimal strategy.

2. ELECTRIC VEHICLE CHARGING PROFILES

Processes user charging requirements to generate **optimised profiles** that ensure the **desired energy level** is reached within the available time window. This enables flexible yet reliable EV charging aligned with grid conditions.

3. COMMUNITY NET POWER

Calculates the **net power exchanged between the community and the grid**. This parameter captures both imported and exported energy, providing insights into grid interactions and renewable utilisation. Analysing this variable alongside renewable generation, stored energy, and demand patterns enables improved system-level optimisation.

4. ADDITIONAL INDICATORS

Generates **complementary data** such as the total power exchanged by each community member, aggregate energy costs, and other demand-side indicators. These variables are essential for evaluating the service's performance and conducting advanced energy management analyses.

4

DEDALUS Use cases

This chapter presents a series of **use cases** developed within the project's pilot sites.

Each case illustrates how technological innovation, data-driven modelling, and user engagement converge to enable **residential energy and comfort flexibility** in diverse European contexts — from individual apartments to community-scale systems.

The selected examples are not only technical demonstrations, but also educational resources designed to help students and practitioners understand the interplay between data, human behaviour, and energy management.

They provide concrete insights into:

- how the **energy flexibility tool quantifies** flexibility potential and supports predictive planning;
- how the **comfort flexibility service** integrates user feedback to maintain well-being during DR events;
- and how the **district-level energy management system** coordinates shared assets to maximise renewable self-consumption and grid stability.

Together, these case studies show how the **DEDALUS approach** can be scaled and adapted to different social, climatic, and regulatory settings - offering a hands-on understanding of what user-centred flexibility means in practice.

4.1 FLEXIBILITY ASSESSMENT TOOL AT THE AUSTRIAN & GREEK PILOTS

For the aggregated flexibility analysis, the residential building selected as a case study is located in Wiener Neustadt, Austria.

The building consists of 44 apartments separated into two floors, and for each floor there is a dedicated PV system that supplies electricity. The data collected includes **data on the energy consumption** of the first-floor energy meter and **data on the energy production** of the PV system that supplies this floor. The dataset tested on the tool spans two years with one-hour granularity, providing a comprehensive foundation for analyses and subsequent modelling efforts. The Austrian user starts at the homepage, which provides an overview of the tool and its intended users. Then the user is prompted to log in to access the platform.

After logging in, users are presented with the ‘Select Country’ page, where they choose the country (in this case Austria) in which they want to perform their analysis. Once the country is selected, users choose between **aggregated** or **disaggregated** levels of analysis, giving them flexibility depending on their specific needs.

After selecting the analysis level (aggregated in this case), users are directed to the data insertion page, where they can review the data requirements and explore a sample dataset.

In the Data Analytics Section (Fig. 4), users view the results of their data analysis, including total, average, and maximum consumption and generation along with granular insights such as daily average load profiles and flexibility estimations for the past week. This detailed visualisation allows for precise monitoring of energy consumption and production trends.

The Austrian pilot. Credits: OurPower

FIG. 4

Data Analytics Dashboard for Aggregated Flexibility

Finally, users are taken to the forecasts page (Fig. 5), where they can see predictions based on the data they uploaded, displayed across time ranges (1 day, 3 days, etc.). Additionally, users receive calculated energy flexibility indicators (EFIs), which show the flexibility of energy consumption and production for different times of the day. In more detail (Fig. 6), the user can see the calculated EFIs in the form of two charts, the EFI UP & DOWN per hour of the day, and the distribution of the EFI categories within the day. Suggestions for load shifting, based on these flexibility metrics, are also provided based on the EFIs.

FIG. 5 e 6

Forecasts Dashboard for Aggregated flexibility

FIG. 7

Data Analytics Dashboard for Disaggregated Flexibility

For the disaggregated use case, the FLEXiT was applied to smart meter data from a residential building participating at the Greek HERON pilot. The dataset contains high-resolution building electricity consumption (1-minute granularity), covering several months of operation.

After logging in, the user selects Greece on the country selection page and chooses the Disaggregated Analysis option. On the Data Insertion page, the user reviews the specific requirements for disaggregated analysis (time resolution, maximum file size and optional PV production) and uploads the dataset. The user then configures the forecasting model (either creating a new one or selecting an existing one) and selects which appliances to include in the analysis.

In the Disaggregated Data Analytics dashboard (Fig. 7), the tool summarises total household consumption over the last 30 days, including total energy used, average daily load and the maximum daily peak. Below, a high-resolution

FIG. 8
Forecasts Dashboard for Disaggregated Flexibility

time-series chart displays minute-level demand, while daily and hourly average load profiles reveal typical usage patterns and high-load periods across the day. This helps the user understand when appliances are normally active and where flexibility potential is concentrated.

On the Disaggregated Forecasts dashboard (Fig. 8), the tool provides short-term forecasts (up to three hours ahead) of total and appliance-level

consumption. One chart shows the aggregated forecast for total demand, while another breaks it down by device, indicating which appliances are expected to drive upcoming peaks. A dedicated plot compares real vs. predicted consumption for the last day, allowing the user to visually assess forecast accuracy. Finally, the disaggregated flexibility forecast is displayed as a percentage curve over time, indicating how much of the predicted load can be shifted or curtailed in each time slot. Based on this, the tool highlights time windows where shifting flexible appliances (e.g. dishwasher or washing machine cycles) can reduce peaks and improve alignment with system needs.

4.2 COMFORT FLEXIBILITY SERVICE AT THE ITALIAN PILOT

The Italian use case illustrates how the Comfort Flexibility Service operates in a real residential context, focusing on elderly occupants living at the Borgo Mazzini Smart Cohousing (BMSC) in Treviso. This environment provides a highly relevant setting for assessing comfort-based flexibility, given the residents' diverse comfort needs and the building's centralised management of indoor conditions.

The Italian pilot. Credits: AdrianoMarangon©MADEassociat

BMSC is located in the historic centre of Treviso and hosts around 80 elderly residents. Each person lives in an independent one- or two-bedroom apartment of approximately 40–50 m². The units are fully equipped for autonomous living and designed according to **Design4All principles**, ensuring accessibility and ease of use. These features allow the apartments to remain suitable for independent living as residents' mobility or health conditions change over time.

FIG. 9

Notifications and Comfort Feedback

Notification sent to residents via Telegram app

Questionnaire used to collect TSV

While these apartments are designed to be as comfortable as possible, the heating, cooling, energy and water supplies are all managed centrally by Istituto per Servizi di Ricovero e Assistenza agli Anziani (ISRAA), the organisation in charge of these buildings. This centralised approach can sometimes create differences in comfort perception, as each resident has their own unique needs. In this educational kit, the focus is on one of the buildings in BMSC.

All environmental measurements and survey-based comfort feedback are used to train a machine learning model capable of predicting residents' thermal comfort in real time using only environmental inputs. This allows the system to infer comfort levels without requiring continuous resident input.

Once these measurements are consolidated into an hourly dataset, they are processed by the comfort flexibility model to generate the three recommendations previously described and deliver them to the end-user. This approach is applied in each apartment of the building under study.

SENSOR	MEASURED PARAMETER	ACCURACY
Temperature sensor	Air temperature [°C]	±1.0°C
Humidity sensor	Relative humidity [%]	±3%
CO ₂ sensor	CO ₂ concentration [ppm]	±30 ppm
Lux meter	Light intensity [lux]	±1%
PM 10	Particular matter 10 [µm/m ³]	±10%
PM2.5	Particular matter 2.5 [µm/m ³]	±10%
PM4	Particular matter 4 [µm/m ³]	±10%
PM1	Particular matter 1 [µm/m ³]	±10%
PM0.5	Particular matter 0.5 [µm/m ³]	±10%

Datasheet of the sensors deployed in the Italian Pilot

The comfort flexibility model generates personalised recommendations for the following day, which are shared with either the elderly residents or an ISRAA manager. The selected option is then applied during demand response events to balance user comfort with the grid's operational requirements.

4.3 DISTRICT-LEVEL ENERGY MANAGEMENT SYSTEM AT THE AUSTRIAN PILOT

To exemplify a real-case demonstration, let this service be applied to the residential building of the Austrian Pilot. As previously described, this community has a solar installation that provides renewable generation for self-consumption. The electrical demand of the building's floors is periodically monitored so that **prediction models can be trained to forecast the non-flexible load demand**. To get the most out of the solar production, the community also has several shared electrical batteries with different capacities and power rates, as well as charging points for residents' electric vehicles, which represent the flexible demand of the community. This type of configuration can be considered typical for a residential scenario.

As this service operates at the district-level or supervisory level, its outputs are intended to be processed by the Building Management System (BMS) and are typically accessed only by the building manager rather than by end users on a daily basis. To support this functionality, a communications architecture is required to ensure the reliable signal transmission among the diverse devices involved. Fig.10 shows a general schematic of a deployment platform. All sensors and actuators installed across the solar panels and building facilities are interface with the BMS, which is responsible for collecting and monitoring the data, as well as for transmitting it to other layers of the architecture.

FIG. 10
A typical community configuration for energy management.

For example, in a pre-aggregation framework, the received data, i.e., the measurements from the PV sensors and user's devices are processed to generate forecasts of the day-ahead solar power production and the non-flexible load associated with residents' consumption (e.g., white appliances, HVAC systems, and other electric assets). These forecasts, presented as a time series with a predefined granularity (e.g., 30 minutes), are then passed to the EMS. Other information, such as the state of charge of shared batteries and the charging requirements for electric vehicles, is also transmitted via the BMS.

Once the service (EMS) has received the required inputs, it executes a predefined optimisation algorithm and generates recommendations for the day ahead asset management. As the EMS is part of a cloud infrastructure, its output format is designed to be easily sent back to the pre-aggregation framework, which then transmits it using a Universal Secure Gateway (USG). At this stage of the process, the management recommendations are properly adapted to the actuators and asset control protocols.

For the Austrian Pilot, the EMS is activated daily at 22:00 (local time) to compute the management commands for the following day. The workflow is presented in Fig.11. Among the service outputs, there are schedules for charging and discharging the shared batteries and the EVs in the form of specified power rates for each time window. With the above information, the local controllers will automatically operate the assets.

FIG. 11

Energy management system workflow

FIG. 12

Operation of the EMS from May 26–30, 2025 under the self-consumption maximisation objective

Fig.12 illustrates the service operation under self-consumption maximisation during the course of a week. To interpret the results, the consumption forecast has been combined with the power required for EVs charging, representing nonflexible and flexible demands respectively, and is tagged as Total consumption. The power profiles of five shared batteries are aggregated under the label Storage. The Net power curve indicates the energy either supplied to the community or fed back to the grid. Energy prices are also included to support a better qualitative interpretation of the results. As expected, Fig.16 shows that most of the renewable and stored energy is used to meet local demand, thereby reducing the amount of power drawn from the grid.

FIG. 13

Expected SOC of the EVs when charged under the EMS operation

Finally, Fig.13 shows how the service provides charging profiles for three EVs by distributing the charging power across the available time window (8:00 – 17:00) to gradually reach the minimum required state of charge (SOC) of 80 % by 17:00.

5

Conclusions

The DEDALUS project introduces a comprehensive suite of innovative services designed to enable and optimise **energy flexibility** in the residential sector.

The **flexibility assessment** tool lays the foundation for **informed flexibility management** by identifying the available potential at the apartment, building, or district level. By leveraging **consumption forecasts, load disaggregation, and aggregated indicators**, the tool can determine the **most suitable time windows** for flexibility activation. This predictive insight allows residents, building managers, aggregators and other stakeholders to plan effectively and participate more efficiently in **demand response events**.

Complementing this, the **comfort flexibility service** introduces a novel approach that prioritises residents' health and comfort during energy flexibility operations. Through a combination of **indoor environmental sensing** (thermal, acoustic, visual, and air quality), weather data, and **user feedback** (TSV), the system learns individual **comfort preferences**. This enables the generation of **personalised recommendations** that strike a balance between comfort, energy consumption, and building performance. During DR events, users or managers can select the preferred comfort profile based on their needs or grid requirements, ensuring a flexible yet **human-centered approach** to demand-side management.

Finally, the **district-level energy management system** addresses flexibility at a broader scale by coordinating the use of **shared assets** within residential communities. The service takes into account the configuration of energy resources, **renewable generation forecasts**, and user requirements, such as electric vehicle charging, to solve an **optimisation problem** that minimises energy costs while meeting operational constraints. It generates optimal **schedules for shared battery storage, EV charging**, and overall energy exchange with the grid. The system is designed to operate within a **modular architecture** and communicate seamlessly with other services, enabling integrated, **scalable, and economically efficient district-level flexibility**.

Together, these services establish an **adaptable and interoperable ecosystem for residential DR**. DEDALUS not only empowers users and building operators to actively contribute to grid stability but also ensures that this participation is economically advantageous and aligned with individual comfort and community-wide sustainability goals.

What you learned

By completing this educational kit, you have gained a comprehensive understanding of how residential buildings and communities can actively contribute to Europe's energy transition through innovative, human-centred flexibility solutions. You have learned:

1. WHY RESIDENTIAL DEMAND RESPONSE MATTERS

- Buildings represent a major share of Europe's energy consumption.
- The rise of renewable energy requires new ways to balance demand and supply.
- Residential DR helps achieve this balance while supporting comfort, affordability, and grid stability.

2. THE DEDALUS APPROACH

- DEDALUS integrates **social**, **technological**, and **business** dimensions to create inclusive and scalable DR ecosystems.
- You explored how people's comfort, behaviours and motivations are as important as technical infrastructures.

3. THE THREE DEDALUS SERVICES

- **Energy Flexibility Tool:** You learned how data-driven methods - forecasts, baselines, EFIs, and NILM - quantify flexibility potential at building and device level, enabling smarter planning and operation of energy systems.
- **Comfort Flexibility Service:** You discovered how indoor environmental data, user feedback (TSV), and machine learning models can guarantee occupants' comfort while contributing to DR events in a personalised, adaptive way.

- **District-level Energy Management System:** You explored how communities can coordinate shared assets - PV, batteries, EV charging - to maximise self-consumption, reduce energy costs, and support grid resilience through multi-commodity optimisation.

4. REAL PILOT DEMONSTRATIONS

- You examined practical use cases from Austria, Greece, Italy and other DEDALUS sites.
- You saw how flexibility is assessed, how comfort is managed in real homes, and how community-level optimisation works under actual operating conditions.

5. HOW PREVIOUS EU PROJECTS ENABLED DEDALUS

- Through the Annex, you learned how Horizon 2020 and Horizon Europe initiatives—such as MATRYCS, BD4NRG, DigiBUILD and others—have contributed methodologies, tools, and insights that shape today’s residential flexibility landscape.

BY NOW, YOU SHOULD BE ABLE TO:

EXPLAIN what residential flexibility and DR are, and why they matter.

IDENTIFY the main barriers and enablers for residential participation in DR.

UNDERSTAND how data, digital tools, and comfort models support flexibility services.

INTERPRET basic flexibility metrics such as EFIs, baselines, and load forecasts.

DESCRIBE how a district-level EMS coordinates shared resources within an energy community.

RECOGNISE how social acceptance, user comfort, and behavioural insights are central to DR adoption.

IN OTHER WORDS...

You now have the knowledge to understand and contribute to the future of smart, flexible, and inclusive energy systems in Europe.

Annex

This Annex summarises the **European research and innovation projects** that laid the groundwork for DEDALUS. These initiatives - including **BD4NRG, BIM-SPEED, DigiBUILD, I-ENERGY, MATRYCS, MUSE GRIDS, P2endure, SunHorizon** - have advanced data-driven energy management, local flexibility markets, and citizen engagement. Their results collectively informed the **DEDALUS approach**, which builds on these experiences to develop a **human-centred, multi-energy Demand Response ecosystem** for residential buildings and communities.

BD4NRG

Big Data for Next Generation Energy¹¹

Grant Agreement: 872613.

Funding Programme: Horizon 2020

BD4NRG has delivered an **integrated big data and AI framework** designed to unlock the value of decentralised energy systems, demonstrating how advanced data governance and analytics can strengthen decision-making across the entire energy value chain. The project addressed long-standing barriers - such as fragmented data architectures and regulatory constraints on data sharing - by developing a unified and interoperable reference architecture for Smart Energy. This architecture aligns BDVA SRIA, IDSA, and FIWARE specifications, incorporates SAREF standards, and extends the COSMAG framework, enabling secure multi-party data exchange and full compatibility with operational smart grid environments.

Building on this foundation, BD4NRG matured a **series of technology enablers, including sovereignty-preserving hybrid DLT/off-chain data governance, elastic big data pipelines, IoT/edge-AI-based federated learning, and a tokenised multi-resource marketplace**. These components were integrated into a TRL8 modular analytics toolbox acting as a one-stop shop for developing advanced services by orchestrating existing and third-party datasets, models, and computational resources.

The framework was validated through **thirteen large-scale pilots** deployed by a wide spectrum of energy actors - TSOs, DSOs, aggregators, renewable and storage operators, ESCOs, energy communities, market operators, municipalities, and financial institutions - ensuring coverage of the full energy value chain. To secure long-term impact and uptake, BD4NRG established the SGBDAA Alliance, a data-driven ecosystem that federates new data providers, supports SMEs through cascading funding, and lays the groundwork for hybrid energy-industry digital platforms.

BIM-SPEED

Harmonised Building Information Speedway for Energy-Efficient Renovation¹⁰

Grant Agreement: 820553

Funding Programme: Horizon 2020

BIM-SPEED has delivered an **integrated and interoperable BIM-based framework that demonstrates how digital renovation workflows can meaningfully accelerate deep renovation across the EU**. Over four years, the project developed a cloud platform that unifies the entire renovation process - from As-Built data acquisition and modelling to simulation, design assessment, and implementation - offering all stakeholders a free and accessible environment for coordinated decision-making.

To support this platform, BIM-SPEED created a **consistent set of interoperable tools for data management, energy performance simulation, visualisation, and the integration of building and HVAC components**. Particular attention was given to the development of plug-and-play solutions that enable rapid installation in existing buildings, reducing on-site time while ensuring full compatibility with the diverse conditions of Europe's residential stock. These solutions were validated through twelve demonstration cases, which confirmed their technical soundness and practical value in real renovation contexts.

Throughout the project, BIM-SPEED also fostered market uptake. The EU-wide BIM Competition, organised with major European umbrella organisations, catalysed the first large-scale replication effort and led to the launch of more than two hundred BIM-based renovation projects.

DigiBUILD

From physical data silos to digital storage for data

Grant Agreement: 101069658

Funding Programme: Horizon Europe

DigiBUILD moved beyond traditional siloed data approaches by enabling digital, smart and interoperable buildings centred on stakeholder needs.

The project sought to unlock the value of high-quality data and next-generation digital building services, supporting the development of an EU-wide Framework for a Digital Building Logbook.

To achieve this, DigiBUILD created an **open, cloud-based and interoperable toolbox** designed to transform isolated buildings into data-rich, connected and smarter environments. This toolbox supported informed decision-making across performance monitoring, infrastructure planning, policy design and investment de-risking. The project adopted an inclusive, multi-stakeholder co-design approach - aligned with the New European Bauhaus - to ensure end-user-oriented services.

Built on existing EU platforms and initiatives, the solution advanced an emerging **energy-efficient building data space**, leveraging FIWARE, GAIA-X and IDSA frameworks. On top of this governance layer, DigiBUILD developed **AI-based analytics and digital building twins**, enabling transparency, trust and improved information sharing across the built-environment value chain. These solutions were demonstrated under **TRL 8 across ten real-world sites**. DigiBUILD contributed to accelerating the uptake of digital technologies in the building sector, supporting Member States in aligning long-term renovation strategies with EPBD requirements and in progressing towards a climate-neutral building stock by 2050.

I-ENERGY

Artificial Intelligence for Next Generation Energy¹²

Grant Agreement: 101016508

Funding Programme: Horizon 2020

I-ENERGY has delivered an **integrated AI framework designed to accelerate the adoption of advanced analytics and digital intelligence across the**

energy value chain, demonstrating how AI can enhance operational efficiency, support environmental sustainability, and generate broader social value. The project addressed long-standing barriers - such as uncertain business cases, fragmented regulations, immature standards and limited AI skills among SMEs - by creating the conditions for a more mature, accessible and innovation-driven AI ecosystem for the energy sector.

Central to I-ENERGY is an **open, modular framework that supports AI-on-Demand for energy applications by capitalising on state-of-the-art AI, IoT, semantic modelling, federated learning, and advanced analytics**. This framework enables interoperable, sovereignty-preserving and regulation-compliant data handling across multiple stakeholders, ensuring that AI solutions can be deployed reliably and at scale. Alongside the technical framework, I-ENERGY provided direct financial support to SMEs through Open Calls, enabling them to validate new use cases, develop AI building blocks and create innovative AI-based energy services while increasing their competitiveness and aligning with AI4EU requirements.

The project validated its approach **through nine large-scale pilots** covering the entire energy value chain - from optimised management of renewable assets and improved grid operation to risk assessment for energy-efficiency investments and enhanced participation of local and virtual energy communities in flexibility markets. These pilots also demonstrated synergies with non-energy sectors such as e-mobility, personal safety and assisted living, ensuring that AI-enabled services reach a wide range of end users, including those with low or no technical background.

MATRYCS

Modular Big Data Applications for Holistic Energy Services in Buildings¹³

Grant agreement: 101000158

Funding Programme: Horizon 2020

MATRYCS harnessed the decentralisation of the energy system and advances in IoT, big data, AI and distributed computing to enable data-driven services for improved building energy efficiency. Although numerous building data hubs and vocabularies had emerged, their potential remained underexploited due to

limited interoperability across heterogeneous static and dynamic data sources, ontologies and big data architectures not fully tailored to smart buildings.

To overcome these barriers, MATRYCS delivered an **open Reference Architecture for Smart Energy-Efficient Buildings**, aligning major frameworks and enabling sovereignty-preserving, multi-party B2B data exchange while ensuring interoperability, privacy and cybersecurity compliance. The project also upscaled several TRL 5–6 technology enablers, such as DLT-based data governance, big-data pipeline orchestration, IoT/edge AI federated learning and visual analytics, integrating them into the **TRL 7–8 MATRYCS workbench**.

Furthermore, MATRYCS developed a **TRL 8 modular big-data cloud analytics toolbox** as a one-stop front end for analytics services and validated the full framework across **11 large-scale pilots** involving facility managers, ESCOs, financial institutions, municipalities, construction companies and grid and district heating operators. Finally, the project established the BDA Alliance, a data-driven ecosystem designed to attract new data hubs and SME service providers, supporting EU-wide uptake and replication.

MUSE GRIDS

Multi utility Smart Energy GRIDS¹⁴

Grant Agreement: 824441

Funding Programme: Horizon 2020

MUSE GRIDS demonstrated integrated technological and non-technological solutions for weakly connected areas by improving the interaction among local energy grids. The project sought to maximise local energy independence through optimised management of electricity, heating, and cooling networks, gas and water systems, storage, CHP and renewable energy sources, supported by advanced smart-grid functionalities and user-driven control strategies.

To this end, two large-scale pilots were implemented in distinct contexts—urban Osimo (Italy) and rural Oud-Heverlee (Belgium)—both characterised by limited connection to national grids. These sites tested and promoted the project’s key concepts: the **smart energy system**, integrating multiple energy

vectors with storage to reduce costs and carbon footprint, and the **local energy community**, where citizens can participate in energy exchange to ensure affordable, reliable and low-carbon supply.

Beyond the pilots, MUSE GRIDS extended its approach to **three virtual demo-sites** in India, Israel and Spain, assessing the social and environmental dimensions of multi-energy system transition and directly engaging local communities.

P2Endure

Plug-and-Play product and process innovation for Energy-efficient building deep renovation¹⁶

Grant Agreement: 723391

Funding Programme: Horizon 2020

P2Endure has delivered a **fully integrated framework for deep renovation based on prefabricated Plug-and-Play solutions**, showing how scalable and rapidly deployable components can streamline renovation processes across a wide range of building types, including public, residential and historic structures. The project focused on transforming outdated or inefficient buildings into high-performance environments, ensuring that the proposed solutions remain adaptable and technically robust in diverse real-world conditions.

At the heart of P2Endure is a **suite of SME-driven prefabricated systems supported by 3D printing, laser and thermal scanning, and seamlessly integrated into a BIM-enabled workflow**. This combination enables highly accurate planning and low-disturbance installation, significantly reducing on-site time while enhancing overall renovation quality. Over four years, these innovations were tested in ten large-scale live demonstration projects across four EU geo-clusters, implemented through the “4M” approach - Mapping, Modelling, Making and Monitoring. The results demonstrated clear performance gains: sixty percent energy savings, fifteen percent cost reduction, fifty percent time reduction and consistently high indoor environmental quality. The overall leverage in primary energy saved amounts to 19.121 GWh per year.

To foster replication and market uptake, P2Endure established a **Technology Commercialization Platform**, assembling building owners, public authorities, industrial actors, and SMEs. This ecosystem has created the conditions for wider deployment of P2Endure solutions, supporting scale-up across Europe and strengthening the market position of innovative SMEs.

SunHorizon

Sun coupled innovative heat pumps¹⁵

Grant Agreement: 818329

Funding Programme: Horizon 2020

SunHorizon has delivered **an integrated framework that demonstrates how advanced heat pump technologies, when intelligently combined with high-performance solar systems, can significantly reduce emissions, energy bills and fossil-fuel dependency in residential and tertiary buildings.** The project focused on maturing a suite of innovative heat pump solutions—ranging from thermal compression to adsorption and reversible systems—and validating their performance when coupled with photovoltaic, hybrid and thermal solar collectors. Across its demonstrations, SunHorizon showed that these combined systems can provide reliable heating and cooling while maximising on-site renewable energy use.

At the core of the project is a **cloud-based functional monitoring platform** designed as a comprehensive performance “data mine”. This platform supports the **development of data-driven and KPI-oriented algorithms** for predictive maintenance, enhanced system control, and optimal operational strategies aimed at maximising solar exploitation. It also enables a “robust design under uncertainty” approach, offering manufacturers actionable insights for more accurate system sizing and improved design of future installations. These capabilities extend beyond the specific SunHorizon configurations and can benefit the wider European heating and cooling stock.

The project centred its work on optimised design and engineering of the technologies, smart functional monitoring and KPI-driven management, jointly showcasing the potential for large-scale deployment and market replication of solar-assisted heat pump solutions.

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List of Abbreviations

AI	Artificial Intelligence
BDA	Big Data Alliance
BD4NRG	Big Data for Next Generation Energy
BDVA	Building Information Modelling
BMS	Building Management System
BMSC	Borgo Mazzini Smart Cohousing
B2B	Business to Business
C-DAE	Cluster-Optimised Denoising Autoencoder
CHP	Combined Heat and Power
CO₂	Carbon Dioxide
CFS	Comfort Flexibility Service
COSMAG	COSMAG Framework
DAE	Denoising Autoencoder
DR	Demand Response
DSO	Distribution System Operator
EFIS	Energy Flexibility Indicators
EMS	Energy Management System
ESCO	Energy Service Company
EV	Electric Vehicle
EU	European Union
FIWARE	FIWARE Framework
FLEXIT	Flexibility Assessment Tool
GAIA-X	Federated Data Infrastructure initiative

GWH	Gigawatt Hour
HVAC	Heating Ventilation Air Conditioning
IDSAs	International Data Spaces Association
IEQ	Indoor Environmental Quality
IOT	Internet of Things
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
ISRAA	Istituto per Servizi di Ricovero e Assistenza agli Anziani
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LSTM	Long Short-Term Memory
ML	Machine Learning
NILM	Non-Intrusive Load Monitoring
NTUA	National Technical University of Athens
PV	Photovoltaic
RMSE	Root Mean Square Error
SME	Small and Medium-sized Enterprise
SOC	State of Charge
SRIA	Strategic Research & Innovation Agenda
TSO	Transmission System Operator
TSV	Thermal Sensation Vote
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
UKDALE	UK Domestic Appliance-Level Electricity dataset
USG	Universal Secure Gateway

Disclaimer

All analyses, service descriptions, and data included in this Educational Kit have been provided by the authors. They retain sole responsibility for the accuracy, completeness, and reliability of the information presented.

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